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**A LEXICO-SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF DEVIATIONS IN LANGUAGE USE BY GEN Z
IN NIGERIA**

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Abstract

This article examines lexical and semantic deviations in the language use of Generation Z (Gen Z) in Nigeria, analysing how such deviations function as tools of creativity, identity, and communication in digital spaces. Despite extensive studies on Nigerian English, little attention has been given to the emerging, unconventional linguistic practices of Gen Z, particularly the role of digital technologies in driving their diffusion and the implications for intergenerational communication. The data collection process involved non-participant observation of online conversations, trending hashtags, memes, and other digital interactions. Slang terms and phrases were identified, recorded, and cross-checked with online slang dictionaries, blogs, and user-generated content to ensure reliability. Each lexical item was documented alongside its contextual usage, allowing for an accurate analysis of meaning in practice. This study systematically analyses twenty linguistic data drawn from Instagram, Facebook, and Twitter, focusing on their semantic shifts, lexical innovations, and syntactic deviations from Standard English. Anchored in William Labov's variationist theory (1966), the study adopts a sociolinguistic qualitative design, using purposive sampling to select relevant data and employing qualitative content. Analysis to categorise deviations based on their type, standard meaning, and social meaning. Findings reveal that Gen Z's linguistic practices are not anomalies but deliberate strategies that serve to index social belonging, redefine conventional meanings, and facilitate cultural expressions. The study concludes that language use by Gen Z reshapes the lexico-semantic norms of English, highlighting broader implications for intergenerational communication, linguistic evolution, and sociocultural identity.

Keywords: Deviation, Generation Z, Language, Lexico-semantics.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Nigeria, one of the most linguistically diverse nations in West Africa, provides a rich setting for examining language as a dynamic tool of communication and identity. In the twenty-first century, globalization, technological advancement, and the proliferation of social media have profoundly reshaped language use, particularly among younger generations. Within this landscape, Generation Z those born between the late 1990s and early 2010s has emerged as a cohort whose linguistic creativity reflects both local realities and global cultural flows. The rise of what scholars describe as Nigerian Youth English has developed into an even more distinct register commonly referred to as Gen Z English. This variety is marked by lexical innovation, semantic shifts, and multimodal practices that distinguish it from earlier generational forms. Across platforms such as TikTok, Instagram, Twitter, and Snapchat, Gen Z rapidly circulates and redefines expressions. Words such as stan (from “stalker + fan”), ghosting (abruptly ending communication), and tea (gossip) exemplify how this group adapts language for brevity, humor, and impact. Nigerian examples, including bants (banter), cruise (fun or mischief), and soft life (a life of ease), illustrate how global slang blends with Pidgin English and indigenous languages, producing hybrid forms that are simultaneously global and local.

Lexico-semantic deviation, understood as the repurposing of existing terms, the creation of new lexical items, and the redefinition of meaning, has become a hallmark of Gen Z language. These innovations are not arbitrary but reflect identity, inclusivity, and generational resistance to traditional linguistic norms. Words such as simp and gaslight have been repurposed to capture social dynamics, while acronyms like FOMO (“fear of missing out”) and YOLO (“you only live once”) condense complex ideas into compact, shareable forms. In digital contexts, emojis, GIFs,

and memes further expand meaning, underscoring the participatory and multimodal character of Gen Z communication.

Although studies of Nigerian English have examined multilingualism, code-mixing, and slang (Adegbija; Igboanusi; Adegbite), systematic analyses of the lexico-semantic deviations specific to Gen Z remain scarce. Global research (Tagliamonte; Androutsopoulos; Crystal) has shown how online environments foster linguistic experimentation, but the Nigerian case is underexplored. Questions remain about whether Gen Z lexical innovations are ephemeral or enduring, how multimodal communication reshapes meaning, and what implications these shifts have for intergenerational communication and language norms.

As against this background, the present study identifies the lack of systematic investigation into Gen Z's lexico-semantic deviations in Nigeria as a pressing research gap. While Gen Z's linguistic practices are highly visible in digital spaces, academic attention to their forms, functions, and long-term implications has been limited. This article therefore seeks to examine and categorize the recurring patterns of lexical and semantic deviation in Nigerian Gen Z discourse, analyze the socio-cultural and technological factors driving these practices, and consider their implications for communication across generations and for the future of English in Nigeria. In pursuing these aims, the study addresses the following questions: How do Nigerian Gen Z speakers innovate lexically and semantically? What cultural, social, and technological conditions shape these innovations? And what consequences do these practices carry for language norms, identity construction, and intergenerational communication? By engaging with these questions, the article contributes to scholarship on sociolinguistics and language variation, showing that Gen Z's playful yet

purposeful linguistic practices are central to understanding both contemporary Nigerian English and the global dynamics of youth language.

2.1 LITERATURE REVIEW

Lexico-semantics, also known as lexical semantics, is a subfield of linguistic semantics that focuses on the study of word meaning, its structure, and its relationship with language. Mathew (45) defines it as “the study of word meaning and its relationship with language structure, including the analysis of semantic fields, lexical relations, and the semantic properties of words and phrases”. His account highlights that lexico-semantics investigates not only denotation and connotation but also sense, reference, synonymy, antonymy, hyponymy, and hypernymy. Analysing semantic fields, he argues, offers insight into how meanings are organised within both the mental and social lexicon, while also stressing that lexical meaning cannot be divorced from the influence of syntactic structure. Crystal (10) similarly describes lexico-semantics as “the branch of linguistics which studies the meaning of words and phrases, and the relationships between them”. He emphasises the multifaceted nature of word meaning, the structuring of semantic fields, and the interactions among semantics, grammar, and pragmatics. Hanks (7) advances this view by underscoring the combinatorial nature of lexical meaning, referring to lexico-semantics as “the study of words and their meanings, including the relationships between words and the ways in which words combine to form meaningful expressions”. This notion situates meaning not only in individual lexical items but in their ability to generate coherence when combined in discourse.

Cruse (12) provides a foundational perspective by foregrounding the systematic interrelations of words within the lexicon. He draws attention to semantic relationships such as synonymy, antonymy, hyponymy, and meronymy, which collectively contribute to the structure of meaning

in mental representation and social interaction. Cruse's framework moves beyond the study of isolated word meanings to consider how lexical items function relationally, thereby providing a richer understanding of how communication is shaped through networks of meaning. These perspectives establish lexico-semantics as a key dimension of linguistic inquiry, particularly in understanding how language evolves and adapts across contexts.

The idea of deviation is equally central to linguistic study, particularly in examining how meaning is manipulated or transformed. Deviation, in linguistic terms, refers to departures from established norms of usage, whether in phonology, morphology, lexis, or semantics. Scholars such as Leech (1969) have explored deviation in stylistics, arguing that it is often a source of creativity and innovation in language. In contemporary contexts, deviation is not merely an aberration but a means of linguistic renewal, serving both expressive and identity functions. For instance, Gen Z speakers often deviate from conventional usage through deliberate distortions, creative coinages, and semantic shifts that challenge traditional boundaries of meaning. Such deviations resonate with Labov's theory of variation, which posits that language change emerges from social practice and group identity rather than random alteration. In this sense, deviation is reinterpreted not as error but as a systematic response to cultural, social, and technological influences.

Turning to empirical evidence, several studies have examined language use among Nigerian youth, though few focus exclusively on Gen Z's lexico-semantic deviations. Adegbija's (76) *Multilingualism and Language Contact in Nigeria* explores how code-switching and code-mixing shape Nigerian English, while Igboanusi (112) highlights borrowing, blending, and acronyms as key processes in lexical innovation. Oyebade (204) has investigated the phonology of Nigerian Youth English, showing how sound systems vary across age and social groups, and Ademola (68)

has analysed pragmatic strategies like politeness and implicature in Nigerian youth discourse. In a related study, Ogundipe (69) observed that social media accelerates lexical change among Nigerian youths, creating new domains for experimentation, while Osisanwo (59) compared Nigerian and British English, pointing to differences in vocabulary and syntax influenced by language contact. Ulrike Gut's (98) work on the phonology of Nigerian English further underscores the distinctiveness of Nigerian varieties in a global context. Beyond Nigeria, global studies reveal similar trends: Tagliamonte and Denis (115) found that Canadian youths employ innovative lexical items in online chatrooms, while Androutsopoulos (92) shows how European youth integrate English slang into local varieties as markers of global youth identity. Such studies confirm that youth language is dynamic, hybrid, and socially meaningful.

Emerging research suggests that Gen Z's linguistic behaviour foregrounds creativity and social identity. Their use of lexical innovation, semantic shifts, and hybridised registers demonstrates how lexico-semantics intersects with deviation to produce new modes of expression. Far from random, these practices index generational belonging, cultural participation, and resistance to linguistic conservatism. They also highlight the adaptive nature of language in digital spaces, where brevity, playfulness, and innovation are privileged. However, while global studies have begun to document such patterns, research on these practices in Nigeria remains sparse. Much of the existing scholarship on lexico-semantics (Cruse; Crystal; Hanks; Mathew) and deviation (Leech; Labov) has emerged from Euro-American contexts, offering little attention to the sociolinguistic realities of Nigerian English and its hybrid forms. Furthermore, although Eckardt and Dominicy have shown how platform affordances shape innovation, these analyses do not adequately capture the localised creativity of Nigerian Gen Z speakers.

Thus, while emerging research confirms that Nigerian youth speech is innovative, hybrid, and socially significant, few studies focus directly on Gen Z English as a sociolect, particularly from a lexico-semantic perspective. Whereas much of the Nigerian literature has concentrated on phonology, pragmatics, or code-switching, the semantic innovations of Gen Z remain underexplored. This gap is particularly striking given that Gen Z represents the first generation of true digital natives in Nigeria, whose language practices are shaped simultaneously by local sociolinguistic realities and global digital cultures. Their use of creative neologisms, semantic shifts, and hybridised registers demonstrates a distinct language form that sets them apart not only from older generations but also from earlier studies of Nigerian youth speech. In conclusion, by analysing these practices, the present study addresses an important gap in the literature, showing how Nigerian Gen Z employs lexico-semantic deviation to construct identity, negotiate meaning, and respond to technological and cultural shifts.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored in William Labov's Theory of Linguistic Variation, first articulated in *The Social Stratification of English in New York City* (1966). Central to Labov's framework is the claim that language is systematic and that variation, even when it departs from established norms, is not random but patterned. He demonstrates that linguistic choices are socially stratified, shaped by variables such as age, gender, class, and community, and that they function as resources for signalling social belonging. Of particular relevance are Labov's distinctions between change from above conscious innovations influenced by prestige norms and change from below unconscious, community-driven shifts that often spread organically. In addition, his principle of accountability requires that both innovative and conventional forms be studied to reveal the systematicity of

variation, while his notion of orderly heterogeneity highlights that apparent irregularity in speech conceals structured linguistic and social patterns.

Labov's framework is particularly apt for a lexico-semantic study of Gen Z because it repositions deviation from "error" to "variation," thereby recognising it as a legitimate site of linguistic change. Gen Z's distinctive practices coining new words, shifting meanings, and hybridising registers are not chaotic departures but patterned innovations that align with Labov's idea of variation as socially meaningful. Their lexical creativity exemplifies change from below: unconscious, peer-driven practices that spread rapidly through digital networks. By contrast, change from above helps explain instances where global prestige forms, such as American internet slang or Nigerian urban prestige codes, influence Gen Z usage. Applying the principle of accountability allows this study to capture both the innovative and the residual conventional meanings that co-exist in Gen Z discourse, while the concept of orderly heterogeneity clarifies why their slang, though seemingly unstable, follows regular patterns within the peer group.

The justification for using Labov's framework rests on the theory's ability to bridge structural and social dimensions of language. While semantic innovation has often been analysed descriptively, Labov provides an interpretive model that situates these innovations within broader patterns of social identity and generational difference. His framework underscores that Gen Z's language practices in Nigeria are not isolated phenomena but socially embedded strategies for constructing identity, negotiating belonging, and redefining norms. Thus, by applying Labov's Theory of Variation, this study interprets Gen Z's lexico-semantic deviations not as anomalies but as structured, meaningful, and culturally situated practices that reflect the dynamics of language change in a digital, postcolonial context.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative research design anchored in content analysis, which is appropriate because it allows for systematic description and interpretation of linguistic data. The focus was on how meaning is created, negotiated, and altered in context by Nigerian Gen Z users. Data were drawn purposively from social media platforms such as X formerly Twitter Instagram, and Facebook since these constitute the most active spaces for digital interaction and linguistic innovation among young people. A total of forty lexical items were sampled on the basis of their frequency of use, cultural relevance, and representation of deviation from Standard English and twenty were analysed.

The data collection process involved non-participant observation of online conversations, trending hashtags, memes, and other digital interactions. Slang terms and phrases were identified, recorded, and cross-checked with online slang dictionaries, blogs, and user-generated content to ensure reliability. Each lexical item was documented alongside its contextual usage, allowing for an accurate analysis of meaning in practice.

The analysis was guided by Labov's variationist theory, which views language change as systematic and socially motivated rather than random. Each expression was examined in terms of whether it constituted a lexical innovation, a semantic shift, or a pragmatic deviation. Examples were drawn from real online discourse to illustrate how Gen Z speakers employ these linguistic features in everyday communication. This methodological approach ensured that the study captured both the structural dimensions of deviation and its social significance as a marker of identity and generational belonging.

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA DATA PRESENTATION

S/N	Gen Z Expressions	Lexicosemantic deviation	Standard Meaning	Social Meaning
(A)	(B)	(C)	(D)	(E)
1.	Barney	Semantic shift	Noisy quarrel/fight	Young female
2.	Rizz	Lexical Innovation	Charisma/Charm/F lirt game	Attractiveness
3.	Shame wear me Agbada	Semantic deviation	Deeply ashamed	Emotional Exaggeration
4.	No cap	Idiomatic creation	Seriously	Truth assertion
5.	YOLO	Lexical/Semantic shift You only live once/Reminder of mortality	In-group	Identity marker
6.	Deadass	Intensifier	Seriously	Emphasis
7.	Sus	Clipping + semantic narrowing	Suspicious	Skepticism

8.	Drip	Lexical innovation	Fashionable clothing	Style/status
9.	Goat	Lexical/semantics shift/Acronymic construction	Greatest of all Times	Highly respected/Legendary
(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(e)
10	Vibe check	Nominalization	Evaluate atmosphere	Social harmony
11	Japa	Semantic shift	In-group identity marker	In-group identity marker
12	Its giving	Structure barrowing	Suggest	Evaluation
13	Lykyk Acronym	If you know you know	In-group	Exclusivity
14	Beat	Semantic Shift	Inflict pain	Apply makeup/easthetic/ingroup solidarity
15	Aza	Semantic shift	Mediocre	Criticism/Bank account
16	Flex	Semantic shift	Show off	Boast

17	Simp	Semantic degradation	Over-eager admirer	Submissiveness
18	Ghost	Semantic shift	Disappear without notice	Social disengagement
19	Type shit	Semantic deviation	You know what I mean/in-group solidarity. Depending on context	In-group solidarity
20	Lit	Semantic shift	Exciting	Hight energy

DATA ANALYSIS

4.3.1 Analysis of the Gen Z language use "Barney"

@notoriousCloud on x

This Barney I used to have a huge crush on, saw her recently, my God! Ion know man Is it me, or is makeup, the cake-like kind a huge turnoff?

In analyzing the utterance, This Barney I used to have a huge crush on, saw her recently, my God! Ion know man Is it me, or is makeup, the cake-like kind a huge turnoff? one can observe how the principle that language is systematic, as advanced by William Labov, manifests in Gen Z usage. Labov maintains that even when speakers deviate from standardized linguistic norms, their choices are not random but governed by consistent patterns within social and cultural contexts (Labov 1966). The utterance illustrates this systematicity through semantic shifts, lexical reductions, and stylistic strategies that work together to create meaning in a structured way.

The term Barney, traditionally denoting the purple dinosaur from children's television, undergoes a semantic reassignment as a nickname for a young woman. Although this appears as a deviation from the conventional meaning, it is systematic because it draws upon a shared cultural reference familiar to the community. Within Gen Z discourse, this repurposing of cultural symbols demonstrates an orderly process where words are not arbitrarily transformed but assigned new meanings that serve social bonding, playfulness, and identity construction (Labov 224). The innovation, therefore, reflects patterned lexical creativity within the speech community rather than linguistic chaos.

Similarly, the reduction of I dont to Ion highlights how phonological and orthographic variation follows consistent rules of digital and oral interaction. This abbreviated form is not an error but part of a predictable system of informal communication that indexes group membership and stylistic informality (Labov 202). The expression cake-like kind, though metaphorical, also reflects systematicity in how figurative language is deployed to evaluate and critique appearance. Together, these choices form a coherent system of meaning-making that aligns with Labov's assertion that linguistic variation is structured and patterned. Thus, Gen Z's utterance demonstrates that what

might superficially appear as deviation is in fact a systematic reorganization of language to convey identity, social stance, and shared cultural understanding.

4.3.2 Analysis of the Gen Z Language use " Rizz"

Khan: 99% of your rizz depends on her interest in you

In the expression, 99% of your rizz depends on her interest in you, the lexical item rizz represents a striking example of lexical innovation within Gen Z discourse. Labov's principle that language is systematic emphasizes that linguistic deviations, far from being random, follow identifiable patterns that reveal the structured creativity of speech communities (Labov 1966). The emergence and usage of rizz illustrate this systematicity in both form and meaning, demonstrating how Gen Z speakers modify and restructure language in predictable ways to express identity and social meaning.

Formally, rizz derives from the word charisma through phonological clipping, where the initial syllables are systematically dropped, leaving a shorter, more impactful variant. This process is not arbitrary but reflects a patterned linguistic economy common in youth language, where brevity and memorability are prized. In its word class, rizz functions as a countable noun, referring to a quantifiable measure of one's romantic or social appeal. Its adoption into everyday discourse among Gen Z speakers exemplifies how systematic phonological and morphological processes generate new lexical forms that enhance communicative efficiency while signaling group belonging.

Semantically, rizz undergoes a narrowing shift from the broader meaning of charisma, which in Standard English denotes general charm, magnetism, or leadership qualities across diverse social

domains. In Gen Z usage, however, rizz is contextually constrained to romantic and sexual attractiveness, particularly one's ability to successfully engage in flirting or courtship. This narrowing follows a systematic pattern of meaning specialization observed in linguistic communities, where broad terms are adapted to fulfill more specific social functions (Labov 224). Thus, the use of rizz demonstrates how Gen Z speakers reorganize language systematically to encode shared values, highlight social identity, and articulate context-bound meanings.

4.3.3 Analysis of the Gen Z language use "Wear me Agbada"

Otaibayomi: "Shame wear me agbada put fila for this gender"

In the Gen Z expression, shame wear me agbada put fila for this gender, the principle that language is systematic, as outlined by William Labov, becomes evident. Labov argues that linguistic variations, even when they appear as deviations from standardized norms, operate within an ordered system shaped by social and cultural contexts (Labov 1972). This utterance demonstrates that Gen Z linguistic creativity is not random but follows structured semantic and lexical patterns that reflect both cultural symbolism and social identity.

Lexically, the word shame is personified as an active agent capable of dressing the speaker, which represents a systematic deviation from its conventional abstract use. The construction wears me agbada functions metaphorically, where the "agbada" a flowing Yoruba attire often associated with grandeur is reinterpreted as a symbol of being heavily draped in disgrace. The addition of put fila extends the metaphor, intensifying the imagery by suggesting that shame not only clothes the speaker but completes the attire with a cap, thereby signifying total humiliation. Each of these

elements follows a predictable cultural logic, drawing from shared knowledge of traditional Nigerian attire to structure a vivid representation of public embarrassment.

Semantically, the phrase illustrates a consistent system of metaphorical extension. Rather than literal clothing, agbada and fila encode symbolic meanings of excess, exposure, and ridicule. The ironic use of this gender further situates the expression within a framework of generational and social commentary, indexing identity and collective experience. According to Labov's principle of systematicity, such deviations reveal ordered processes of meaning-making: shame is transformed into an embodied actor, attire becomes a metaphor for disgrace, and cultural symbols are repurposed to communicate intensity of emotion. Thus, this utterance exemplifies how Gen Z speakers systematically manipulate language to encode identity, negotiate social stance, and foster solidarity, affirming Labov's insight that linguistic variation, however unconventional, remains structured and rule-governed.

4.3.4 Analysis of the Gen Z language use #No cap:

Kuyak James: #No cap, When God said he will bless the works of my hands, I took it personal.

In the expression, #No cap, When God said he will bless the works of my hands, I took it personal, the lexical item no cap demonstrates Labov's principle that language is systematic. While cap in Standard English denotes a form of headwear, in African American Vernacular English it underwent a semantic shift to mean to lie or to exaggerate. The negated form no cap systematically extends this innovation, creating a fixed idiomatic expression that signifies truth or sincerity. This shift shows that even apparent deviations follow structured linguistic processes rather than random usage (Labov 1966).

Lexically, the innovation involves reassigning a common noun to a figurative sense unrelated to its original denotation, a process Labov identifies as part of systematic variation within communities. Semantically, the phrase undergoes bleaching and reanalysis, moving from the literal domain of objects (cap as clothing) to the abstract domain of evaluation (no cap as truth-claim). This progression reflects a patterned narrowing of meaning, as the term is stabilized within Gen Z usage to denote authenticity, particularly in contexts of personal emphasis or social assertion.

Thus, the phrase no cap illustrates how Gen Z speakers systematically restructure lexical and semantic resources to generate new meanings. The deviation is not arbitrary but reflects ordered patterns of of evaluation (no cap as truth-claim). This progression reflects a patterned narrowing of meaning, as the term is stabilized within Gen Z usage to denote authenticity, particularly in contexts of personal emphasis or social assertion.

Thus, the phrase no cap illustrates how Gen Z speakers systematically restructure lexical and semantic resources to generate new meanings. The deviation is not arbitrary but reflects ordered patterns of semantic shift and lexical repurposing, affirming Labov's observation that linguistic change and innovation operate within consistent systems of variation.

4.3.5 Analysis of the Gen Z language use "YOLO"

Golden Muse: Remember You Only Live Once. Ensure you are living and not merely existing.

#YOLO

In the expression, Remember You Only Live Once. Ensure you are living and not merely existing, the lexical item YOLO illustrates Labov's principle that language is systematic. Though originally a pop-culture slogan associated with recklessness or impulsive enjoyment, YOLO undergoes a

systematic process of semantic recontextualization. Rather than signaling carefree spontaneity, the term here functions as a philosophical imperative, urging purposeful and intentional living. This semantic shift demonstrates that linguistic innovations among Gen Z follow patterned processes of meaning extension rather than random alteration (Labov 1966).

Lexically, YOLO represents an acronymic condensation of the phrase You Only Live Once. Its economy of form, achieved through abbreviation, reflects a systematic tendency toward brevity in youth language. Semantically, the expression shifts from an informal justification for risk-taking to a motivational marker, illustrating a reorganization of meaning along predictable lines of re-evaluation and re-assignment. Furthermore, the opposition in living and not merely existing creates a systematic semantic contrast, embedding evaluative meaning within common vocabulary to construct a moral dichotomy.

Thus, the use of YOLO in this context exemplifies how Gen Z speakers systematically reshape lexical items through abbreviation, semantic recontextualization, and evaluative contrast. The deviation is not arbitrary but reflects structured processes of meaning-making, affirming Labov's (1966) observation that linguistic change and variation are orderly and socially grounded.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

The analysis of the data reveals that Gen Z language use in Nigeria is characterised by systematic patterns of lexico-semantic deviation that extend beyond words into multimodal creativity. These linguistic innovations are achieved through processes such as semantic shift, lexical innovation, clipping, idiomatic creation, intensification, and acronymic construction. Crucially, the findings also show that emojis function as semiotic resources that complement, reinforce, or substitute

verbal expression, thereby creating multimodal forms of communication that are socially and culturally significant. Together, these deviations highlight how Gen Z reshapes communicative norms by combining verbal ingenuity with visual symbolism.

A central pattern observed is the pervasiveness of semantic shift. Words such as Barney (from quarrel to young female), Japa (from “to run” to “to emigrate”), Beat (from “inflict pain” to “apply makeup”), and Ghost (from “spectre” to “withdraw from interaction”) illustrate how existing lexical items acquire novel meanings that reflect generational experiences. For instance, Japa, originally from Yoruba, has been semantically extended to describe emigration in response to socio-economic challenges and is often reinforced with the ✈️ emoji in digital spaces. Such instances show how Gen Z strategically recontextualises language to address contemporary realities while embedding their expressions in global digital symbolism.

Lexical innovation is equally pronounced. Terms like Rizz (charisma or flirt game) and Drip (fashion sense) exemplify how Gen Z coins neologisms that encapsulate lifestyle and identity. These expressions frequently appear with emojis that heighten meaning: Rizz with 💘 conveys flirtatious charm, while Drip is often paired with 😎 to denote confidence and prestige. In this way, innovation is not confined to verbal creation but extends to visual reinforcement, emphasising Gen Z’s performative approach to self-presentation in online and offline contexts.

The findings further reveal the role of acronyms and clippings in shaping Gen Z discourse. Acronyms such as YOLO (You only live once), GOAT (Greatest of All Times), and Iykyk (If you know, you know), alongside clippings like Sus (suspicious), demonstrate the compression of meaning into concise, technologically efficient forms. These items thrive in digital communication

where brevity is prized. They also function as in-group markers, signalling shared knowledge and reinforcing exclusivity. Emojis often complement these compressed forms, as in the use of 🤪 with Deadass, which dramatizes seriousness with humour.

Equally salient is the use of idiomatic and figurative expressions. Phrases such as Shame wear me Agbada and No cap show how exaggeration and idiomatic creation enhance humour, solidarity, and emotional expressiveness. The phrase Deadass, frequently accompanied by the 🤪 emoji, illustrates how intensifiers and visual cues converge to dramatise emphasis. Similarly, Mood combined with 😊 or 😄 operates as a flexible cultural shorthand, turning personal feelings into widely relatable expressions. These examples highlight how figurative language and multimodal cues interact to enrich meaning and foster group solidarity.

5.1 SUMMARY

his study explored the lexico-semantic deviations in the language practices of Gen Z in Nigeria, analyzing how they reshape English through creativity, borrowing, semantic shift, and multimodal expression. Using Labov's variationist theory, the research demonstrated that these deviations are socially motivated and systematically patterned, functioning as tools for identity construction and generational belonging.

In summary, the study identified that Gen Z frequently employs lexical innovations such as "Rizz," "YOLO," and "Soft Life," semantic shifts such as "Ghost," "Flex," and "Mood," and multimodal practices involving emojis like 🔥, 🤔, 🧟, and 😏. These forms are not arbitrary but deliberate, reflecting global cultural flows, digital immediacy, and local socio-cultural realities.

5.2 CONCLUSION

This study set out to investigate the distinctive lexico-semantic practices of Generation Z in Nigeria through three central questions: What forms of lexico-semantic deviations characterise Gen Z English? What socio-cultural and technological forces drive these deviations? And what are their broader implications for communication and language evolution? The findings provide clear answers to each of these questions.

To the first question, the study shows that Gen Z English is defined by systematic lexico-semantic deviations, including semantic shift, lexical innovation, clipping, idiomatic creation, intensification, and acronymic construction. These deviations are not arbitrary but patterned, as seen in items such as Rizz, Japa, Barney, and No cap. Their multimodal reinforcement through emojis such as ✈️ with Japa or 🔥 with Lit further demonstrates that Gen Z expands the expressive resources of English by fusing verbal and visual codes.

To the second question, the analysis demonstrates that Gen Z linguistic practices are driven by identifiable socio-cultural trends and digital technologies. Expressions such as Soft Life capture aspirations for comfort and status, while Japa reflects socio-economic pressures linked to migration. Borrowings from African American Vernacular English, such as Lit and GOAT, illustrate global cultural flows, while emoji pairings underscore the affordances of digital platforms. Gen Z thus innovates within language as a way of negotiating identity, solidarity, and cultural relevance in both local and global contexts.

Finally, to the third question, the study concludes that these practices hold significant implications for communication and language evolution. Gen Z English challenges traditional notions of

correctness by showing that deviation is a creative reconfiguration of meaning rather than linguistic corruption. Their practices expand the semantic and expressive range of English, strengthen in-group solidarity, and contribute to the dynamism of Nigerian and global English. In doing so, Gen Z emerges as a key driver of contemporary linguistic change.

From these findings, three recommendations follow. First, linguists and educators should recognise Gen Z English as evidence of English's vitality, not decline, and integrate its examples into research and pedagogy. Second, fostering intergenerational awareness of these practices can reduce communication gaps and promote mutual understanding. Third, continued research is needed to trace the lifecycle, diffusion, and possible mainstreaming of Gen Z expressions across different social and regional contexts.

In conclusion, the study affirms that Gen Z's language practices highlight the evolving relationship between technology, culture, and communication. Their deliberate innovations, both verbal and multimodal, reveal that deviation is not a threat to English but a sign of its adaptability and resilience in a rapidly changing world.

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